

PRINCIPALS' MOTIVATIONAL STRATEGIES AND TEACHERS' PROMOTIONAL QUALITIES: INPUT TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF ENHANCED PERFORMANCE OF ELEMENTARY TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' performance is very important to school success and learners development. Principals play a vital role in motivating the teachers to perform well. This study aimed to determine the perceived motivational strategies of principal and promotional qualities of teacher and its relation on teacher's performance. The respondents of this study are 94 teachers from selected schools of Del Remedio District. This study used descriptive type of research and used a self-made survey questionnaire through google form to analyze the present condition of variables. Results of the study revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between extrinsic and intrinsic motivation and teachers' performance in terms of teaching competence and personal, professional, and social competence. It also suggests that there is no significant relationship between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and teacher's performance in terms of administrative compliance and service to school and community. Therefore, the null hypothesis "there is no significant relationship between principal motivational strategies and teacher's performance" in terms of administrative compliance and service to school and community are partially sustained while, in terms of teaching competence and personal, professional, and social competence are not sustained in this study. Meanwhile the study also revealed that promotional qualities of teachers and teacher's performance have positive significant relationship. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between promotional qualities and teacher's performance is not sustained in the findings of the study.

Keywords: educational management, principal's motivational strategies, promotional qualities, teacher's performance, descriptive type research, Philippines